

Uniform acceleration in a homogeneous field of force - relativistic

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A particle falls in a homogeneous field of force in vacuum. We treat this case relativistically. With Becker [1] p.275,306 it is valid for the covered way, if t is the time and b the classical acceleration and c the light velocity in vacuum:

$$z(t) = \frac{c^2}{b} \cdot \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} - 1 \right)$$

We derive to the time and we obtain the relativistic velocity:

$$v_r = \frac{dz(t)}{dt} = \frac{c^2}{b} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot \frac{b^2}{c^2} \cdot t}{2 \cdot \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}} = \frac{bt}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}}$$

If t is increasing to infinity. We get:

$$\frac{bt}{\left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)} = c$$

Now we derive again and we obtain the relativistic acceleration:

$$\begin{aligned} b_r = \frac{dv_r}{dt} &= \frac{b \cdot \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} - bt \cdot \frac{\frac{b^2 t}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}}}{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} \\ &= \frac{b \cdot \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} - \frac{\left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}} \right)}{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} \end{aligned}$$

If t is increasing to infinity, it follows:

$$\frac{b \cdot \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2} - \frac{bt}{c} \right)}{1 + \left(\frac{bt}{c}\right)^2}$$

The term is decreasing to zero for t to infinity. For very small t we have:

$$\frac{dz(t)}{dt} \approx b \cdot t \qquad \frac{d^2z(t)}{dt^2} \approx b$$

Now we make a numerical calculation to compare relativistic and non-relativistic quantities. It is the acceleration, velocity and the fall path. The light velocity is $c = 300000000$ metres per second. We view the following table with the time t in seconds, the paths z in metres, the velocity v in metres per second and the acceleration b in $\frac{m}{s^2}$ (index r for the relativistic quantity). $b = 10 \frac{m}{s^2}$ shall be temporal constant:

t	b_r	r	v_r	z	z_r
1	10	10	10	5	5.0
10	10	100	100	500	500.0
100	10	1000	1000	50000	50000.0
1000	9.99999998	10000	9999.99999	5000000	5000000.0
10000	9.9999933	100000	99999.9944	500000000	499999987
100000	9.99983334	1000000	999994.444	$5 \cdot 10^{10}$	$4.99995 \cdot 10^{10}$
1000000	9.98335645	10000000	9994449.07	$5 \cdot 10^{12}$	$4.9986 \cdot 10^{12}$
10^7	8.53814968	10^8	94868329.8	$5 \cdot 10^{14}$	$4.8683 \cdot 10^{14}$
$2 \cdot 10^7$	5.76034819	$2 \cdot 10^8$	166410059	$2 \cdot 10^{15}$	$1.8167 \cdot 10^{15}$
$5 \cdot 10^7$	1.36190053	$5 \cdot 10^8$	257247878	$1.25 \cdot 10^{16}$	$8.4929 \cdot 10^{15}$
$8 \cdot 10^7$	0.43289191	$8 \cdot 10^8$	280898753	$3.2 \cdot 10^{16}$	$1.6632 \cdot 10^{16}$
$9 \cdot 10^7$	0.31622777	$9 \cdot 10^8$	284604989	$4.05 \cdot 10^{16}$	$1.946 \cdot 10^{16}$
10^8	0.23725972	10^9	287347886	$5 \cdot 10^{16}$	$2.2321 \cdot 10^{16}$
$2 \cdot 10^8$	0.03264215	$2 \cdot 10^9$	296680906	$2 \cdot 10^{17}$	$5.1671 \cdot 10^{16}$
$3 \cdot 10^8$	0.00985185	$3 \cdot 10^9$	298511157	$4.5 \cdot 10^{17}$	$8.1449 \cdot 10^{16}$
$4 \cdot 10^8$	0.00418340	$4 \cdot 10^9$	299159793	$8 \cdot 10^{17}$	$1.1134 \cdot 10^{17}$
$5 \cdot 10^8$	0.00214839	$5 \cdot 10^9$	299461454	$1.25 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.4127 \cdot 10^{17}$
$6 \cdot 10^8$	0.00124533	$6 \cdot 10^9$	299625702	$1.8 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.7122 \cdot 10^{17}$
$7 \cdot 10^8$	0.00078501	$7 \cdot 10^9$	299724869	$2.45 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.0119 \cdot 10^{17}$
$8 \cdot 10^8$	0.00052623	$8 \cdot 10^9$	299789285	$3.2 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.3117 \cdot 10^{17}$
$9 \cdot 10^8$	0.00036975	$9 \cdot 10^9$	299833472	$4.05 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.6115 \cdot 10^{17}$
10^9	0.00026964	10^{10}	299865091	$5 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.9113 \cdot 10^{17}$

References

- [1] Becker/Sauter "Theorie der Elektrizität" volume 1, Teubner Verlag Stuttgart, 21. edition 1973